

Modeling of acute toxicity by using topological and structural parameters[†]

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Abstract : In the present study we have considered a diverse set of 48 organic compounds and modeled their acute toxicity ($-\log LC_{50}$) values to the fathead minnow using (i) distance-based topological indices, (ii) Randic connectivity, (iii) Kier and Hall valence connectivity indices, (iv) Balaban and Balaban type indices and (v) structural parameters and performed external validation. The metrics such as R^2_{Pred} or Q^2_{ext} are reported to denote excellent quality of external validation.

Keywords : QSTR/QSAR, acute toxicity, multiple regression (MLR).

Introduction

The basic idea of any QSAR study is on the assumption that molecules from the same chemical domain will show similar behavior which is a general observation also. Consequent to this, in the present study we have investigated such a behavior in modeling acute toxicity to the *fathead minnow* of congeneric series of chemicals such as nitro aromatics¹, alkylamines², halogenated hydrocarbons and phenols³, and chlorobenzenes and chloroalmines⁴, using topological as well as physicochemical parameters.

Agrawal *et al.*⁵⁻¹⁰ have reported important models based on narcotic mechanism of action and toxicity data to *Vibrio fischeri* using molecular connectivity. Using these indices they established the effect due to size, shape, branching, steric and polarity on the exhibition of lipophilicity.

Successful QSAR models for acute toxicity have been developed with logarithm of octanol-water partition coefficient ($\log P$)¹¹⁻¹⁵. Most of these studies find a good correlation between $\log P$ and acute toxicity. The bio-uptake of chemicals by fish or other organisms is directly measured through this important parameter.

Needless to state that the lipophilicity, expressed as $\log P$ is an important parameter used in Quantitative-Structure-Activity-Relationship (QSAR) studies.

As stated earlier the aim of present investigation is to obtain a Quantitative-Structure-Toxicity-Relationship (QSTR) model using topological as well as structural parameters in predicting the $-\log LC_{50}$ values (acute toxicity) of 48 organic compounds reported by Eroglu *et al.*¹⁶ (Table 1).

[†]Dedicated to Professor P. V. Khadikar on his 75th birthday.

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Aquatic toxicity $-\log LC_{50}$ (mg/L) : The aquatic toxicity on *pimephales promelas* is expressed as concentration at which the 50% lethality is observed in a test batch of aquatic organism within a 96 h exposure period.

The present data set of 48 organic compounds and

their experimental $-\log LC_{50}$ values were taken from the literature¹⁶ and are reported in Table 1.

It is worthy to mention that, Eroglu *et al.*¹⁶, has calculated several quantum-mechanics-based descriptors for 48 organic compounds and used them for modeling

Table 1. Compounds their observed and estimated toxicity ($-\log LC_{50}$) values

Compd.	Training set	Obs.	Est.	Residual
		$-\log LC_{50}$	$-\log LC_{50}$	Training set
1	1,2-Propanediol	0.838	0.830	0.008
2	Formamide, <i>N,N</i> -dimethyl-	0.839	0.791	0.048
4	Propane, 1,2-dichloro-	2.907	2.986	-0.079
5	2-Butanol	1.305	1.662	-0.357
7	Ethane, 1,1,2,2-tetrachloro-	3.917	3.620	0.297
8	Phenol, 4,4'-(1-methylethylidene)bis-	4.696	4.621	0.075
10	Benzene, 1,2-dichloro-	3.411	4.240	-0.829
11	Propane, 1,2,3-trichloro-	3.346	3.717	-0.371
13	Ethanol, 2-(diethylamino)-	1.818	1.900	-0.082
14	Benzene, 1,4-dichloro-	4.015	4.179	-0.164
16	2,4-Pentanediol, 2-methyl-	1.089	1.844	-0.755
17	2-Propanol, 1-methoxy-	0.637	1.189	-0.552
19	Phenol, 2,4-dichloro-	4.277	4.136	0.141
20	Ethanol, 2-phenoxy-	2.604	2.701	-0.097
22	Acetic acid, butyl ester-	3.810	3.005	0.805
23	Hexanedioic acid-	3.178	2.338	0.840
25	1-Butene, 3,4-dichloro-	4.184	3.588	0.596
26	2-Propanol, 1-phenoxy-	2.735	2.958	-0.223
28	Propane, 2-methoxy-2-methyl-	2.118	2.120	-0.002
29	1-Propanol, 2-phenoxy-	2.735	3.013	-0.278
31	Dipentyl ether	4.690	4.499	0.191
32	Diisopropyl ether	3.040	2.402	0.638
34	Dibutyl ether	3.600	3.772	-0.172
35	Furan	3.040	2.181	0.859
37	2,6-Dimethoxytoluene	3.870	3.924	-0.054
38	2,2,2-Trichloroethanol	2.690	2.771	-0.081
40	1,3-Dichlorobenzene	4.270	4.344	-0.074
41	1,4-Dimethoxybenzene	3.070	3.466	-0.396
43	3,4-Dichlorotoluene	4.740	4.772	-0.032
44	Acetone	0.850	0.958	-0.108
46	Methanol	0.060	0.152	-0.092
47	Cyclohexanone	2.270	1.968	0.302
Compd.	Test set	Obs.	Est.	Residual
		$-\log LC_{50}$	$-\log LC_{50}$	Test set
3	1-Butanol	1.601	1.685	-0.0842
6	Ethane, 1,1,2-trichloro-	3.214	3.151	0.0628
9	2-Propenoic acid, 2-methyl-, methyl ester	2.552	2.548	0.0042
12	2-Butanone, oxime	2.014	2.695	-0.6814

Table-1 (contd.)

15	Ethane, 1,2-dichloro-	2.931	2.694	0.2372
18	Benzene, methyl-	3.549	3.018	0.5310
21	2,4-Pentanedione	2.860	1.688	1.1724
24	Acetic-acid-ethyl ester-	2.583	2.268	0.3148
27	2-Propenoic acid, 2-methyl-, 2-hydroxyethyl ester	2.758	2.278	0.4802
30	Diphenyl ether	4.620	4.810	-0.1897
33	Tetrahydrofuran	1.520	1.320	0.2001
36	Ethanol	-0.510	0.684	-1.1941
39	1,2,4-Trichlorobenzene	4.790	5.094	-0.3042
42	3-Furanmethanol	2.280	1.777	0.5034
45	Acetophenone	2.870	2.763	0.1070
48	Trichloroethene	3.470	3.779	-0.3091

-log LC₅₀ by DFT and HF based descriptors. They have used the entire data set of 48 compounds and presented the final results by considering three outliers. In the present study we have used the same dataset and presented the results using external validation technique.

Parameters used :

Wiener index (*W*) :

The Wiener index¹⁷ (*W*) is defined as the sum of the numbers of edges in the shortest paths in a chemical graph between all pairs of non-hydrogen atoms in a molecule. Mathematically, *W* index is defined as :

$$W = W(G) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n d_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where d_{ij} is the topological distance (minimum) between the two vertices (atoms) *i* and *j*.

Balaban's *J* index :

The average distance sum connectivity index *J* commonly called Balaban *J* index of the molecular graph *G* is defined by the formula¹⁸ :

$$J = \frac{q}{\mu + 1} \sum_{\text{edges } ij} (S_i S_j)^{-1/2} \quad (2)$$

q - number of edges in the molecular graph;

$(q - n + 1)$ = the cyclomatic number of the molecular graph;

n - number of atoms in the molecular graph; and

S_i - distance sums calculated as the sums over the rows or columns of the topological distance matrix of the

molecule, *D*.

Balaban heteroatom index (J_{het}) :

This is an extension of Balaban index (*J*)^{18,19} to molecules containing heteroatoms. In the case of heteroatoms differentiation is made between the atoms of different kinds by modifying the corresponding elements of the distance matrix *D*. For instance, the following modification was suggested for the diagonal elements :

$$(D)_{ii} = 1 - (Z_c/Z_i) \quad (3)$$

where $Z_c = 6$ and Z_i is determined by the number of all electrons of atom *i* or namely Z_i is the atomic number of given elements.

The off-diagonal elements of the modified distance matrix for heteroatom systems are given by the following equation :

$$(D)_{ij} = \sum k_r r \quad (4)$$

where the summation is over *r* bonds.

The bond parameter k_r is given by the following expression :

$$k_r = 1/w_r X (Z_c)^2 / (Z_i + Z_j) \quad (5)$$

where w_r is the bond weight with values of 1, 1.5, 2 and 3 for single, an aromatic, double and triple bond respectively.

Randic molecular connectivity index :

The branching or connectivity index originally defined by Randic²⁰ is referred to as the path-1 molecular connectivity ${}^1\chi$. The value of ${}^1\chi$ reflects both the size and the branching of the structure. It is related to the size of the molecule because when extra atoms and bonds are

added, more terms are added to the summation, and the value grows²¹. ${}^1\chi$ is also related to the degree of branching of the molecule because, when more branching occurs, the denominators for those terms become larger and the terms themselves become smaller, thus decreasing the overall value for the index.

Randic molecular connectivity index is defined as

$$\chi = \sum_{\text{edges } ij} (D_i D_j)^{-1/2} \quad (6)$$

D_i and D_j - the edge degrees (atom connectivities) of the molecular graph.

Randic indices of different orders :

Definition :

$${}^m\chi = \sum_{\text{path}} (D_i D_j \dots D_k)^{-1/2} \quad (7)$$

Kier and Hall valence connectivity indices :

To generalize the molecular connectivity indices and make them more useful for the characterization of organic molecules containing heteroatoms, the following enhancement was developed²¹⁻²³. The valence delta values were used in place of the degree of the node. The delta values are defined by the following expression.

$$\delta^v = Z^v - h$$

where Z^v is the number of valence electrons for the atom, and h is the number of attached hydrogen atoms. Molecular connectivity indices calculated with these delta values are called valence molecular connectivity and are given a superscript v .

Definition :

$${}^m\chi^v = \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \prod_{k=1}^{m+1} \left[\frac{1}{\delta_k^v} \right]^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

$$\delta_k^v = \frac{(Z_k^v - H_k)}{(Z_k - Z_k^v - 1)} - \text{valence connectivity for the } k\text{-th}$$

atom in the molecular graph

Z_k - the total number of electrons in the k -th atom

Z_k^v - the number of valence electrons in the k -th atom

H_k - the number of hydrogen atoms directly attached to the k -th non-hydrogen atom

$m = 0$ - atomic valence connectivity indices

$m = 1$ - one bond path valence connectivity indices

$m = 2$ - two bond fragment valence connectivity indices

$m = 3$ - three contiguous bond fragment valence connectivity indices etc.

Results and discussion

The structures of the 48 organic compounds used (Table 1) in the present study were drawn with the help of ACD-lab software²⁴. Table 1 also records toxicity values in terms of $-\log LC_{50}$ for the compounds used in the present study. The structural parameters along with the octanol-water partition coefficient ($\log P$) are reported in Table 2. The topological (W , J , J_{hetZ} , J_{hetm} , J_{hetv} , J_{hete} , J_{hetP}) and the connectivity based indices (${}^0\chi$, ${}^1\chi$, ${}^2\chi$, ${}^0\chi^v$, ${}^1\chi^v$, ${}^2\chi^v$) were calculated using DRAGON²⁵ software and are summarized in Table 3. The mutual correlations of structural and topological descriptors and their correlations with the experimental activity ($-\log LC_{50}$) for entire dataset are recorded in Table 4.

A perusal of Table 4 shows that $\log P$ and MW have good correlation with $-\log LC_{50}$ as compared to other parameters. Therefore, they are useful in obtaining better models for modeling the acute toxicity ($-\log LC_{50}$).

The study has been performed in three steps :

(a) Taking entire dataset of 48 compounds; (b) Taking 32 compounds as training set; (c) Taking 16 compounds as test set.

Modeling of acute toxicity ($-\log LC_{50}$) is carried out with the help of NCSS software (Kaysville UT, USA). Multiple regression analysis gave several statistically significant models which are reported in Table 5. The crossvalidated parameters were calculated employing leave-one-out Cross-validation procedure²⁶ (Table 7).

The analysis indicated that among all the calculated descriptors four descriptors ($\log P$, MW, J_{hete} , ${}^2\chi^v$) are most suitable for modeling the acute toxicity ($-\log LC_{50}$) of 48 organic compounds. In all the proposed models the $\log P$ is present invariably which means the octanol-water partition coefficient plays a dominant role in modeling the acute toxicity ($-\log LC_{50}$). The step-wise regression yielded following statistically significant models.

Table 2. Calculated values of the physico-chemical parameters used in the present study

Compd.	MW	MR	MV	PC	IR	ST	d	POL	log P
1	76.094	18.970	73.400	182.300	1.430	38.000	1.036	7.520	-0.780
2	73.094	19.850	82.600	186.000	1.396	25.700	0.884	7.870	-0.930
3	74.122	22.110	92.000	208.000	1.395	26.000	0.805	8.760	0.840
4	112.986	25.600	101.200	225.700	1.419	24.700	1.116	10.150	2.250
5	74.122	22.070	92.400	205.400	1.393	24.300	0.801	8.750	0.770
6	133.404	25.820	96.000	224.400	1.450	29.700	1.388	10.230	2.010
7	167.849	30.620	107.800	260.200	1.479	33.900	1.556	12.140	2.190
8	228.286	68.160	199.500	519.700	1.598	46.000	1.143	27.020	3.640
9	102.132	26.940	114.900	253.100	1.385	23.500	0.888	10.680	1.280
10	147.002	36.040	113.300	279.000	1.548	36.700	1.297	14.280	3.280
11	147.431	30.450	112.500	264.200	1.453	30.300	1.309	12.070	2.500
12	87.120	24.510	96.500	219.100	1.421	26.500	0.900	9.710	1.690
13	117.189	35.100	132.300	313.200	1.443	31.400	0.885	13.910	0.050
14	147.002	36.040	113.300	279.000	1.548	36.700	1.297	14.280	3.280
15	98.959	21.010	84.300	188.600	1.412	25.000	1.173	8.330	1.830
16	118.174	32.840	123.000	296.800	1.446	33.800	0.960	13.010	0.580
17	90.121	23.810	98.800	225.000	1.397	26.900	0.912	9.440	-0.490
18	92.138	31.070	105.700	244.900	1.499	28.800	0.871	12.320	2.540
19	163.001	37.920	111.700	294.000	1.593	47.800	1.458	15.030	2.800
20	138.164	39.090	127.400	320.400	1.525	39.900	1.084	15.500	1.100
21	100.116	25.270	105.300	241.200	1.395	27.500	0.950	10.010	0.050
22	116.158	31.620	131.000	295.500	1.397	25.800	0.886	12.530	1.850
23	146.141	32.970	116.800	314.400	1.476	52.400	1.250	13.070	0.230
24	88.105	22.350	98.000	216.000	1.373	23.500	0.898	8.860	0.860
25	124.996	29.960	112.800	254.500	1.443	25.900	1.108	11.870	2.600
26	152.190	43.690	144.300	357.600	1.517	37.600	1.054	17.320	1.520
27	132.158	33.110	128.900	309.700	1.427	33.200	1.024	13.120	0.300
28	88.148	26.920	117.400	245.800	1.375	19.100	0.750	10.670	1.430
29	152.190	43.690	144.300	357.600	1.517	37.600	1.054	17.320	1.520
30	170.207	52.690	160.000	398.300	1.572	38.400	1.063	20.890	4.210
31	158.281	50.120	199.900	449.600	1.415	25.500	0.791	19.870	4.040
32	102.175	31.500	134.600	285.200	1.384	20.100	0.758	12.490	1.520
33	72.106	20.050	79.700	184.700	1.416	28.800	0.904	7.940	0.460
34	130.228	40.850	166.900	370.000	1.404	24.100	0.780	16.190	3.210
35	68.074	18.550	72.200	161.200	1.427	24.800	0.942	7.350	1.340
36	46.068	12.840	59.000	128.400	1.354	22.300	0.780	5.090	-0.310
37	152.190	44.430	153.700	358.200	1.489	29.500	0.990	17.610	2.640
38	149.404	27.360	93.200	238.800	1.498	43.000	1.602	10.840	1.420
39	181.447	40.930	125.200	314.800	1.567	39.900	1.448	16.220	4.050
40	147.002	36.040	113.300	279.000	1.548	36.700	1.297	14.280	3.520
41	138.164	39.600	137.400	320.600	1.488	29.600	1.005	15.700	2.150
42	98.100	25.000	86.000	214.700	1.492	38.800	1.140	9.910	0.300
43	161.029	40.860	129.600	316.600	1.543	35.600	1.242	16.200	4.060
44	58.079	15.970	75.100	156.500	1.345	18.800	0.772	6.330	-0.240
45	120.149	36.280	120.900	292.400	1.511	34.100	0.993	14.380	1.580
46	32.042	8.210	42.500	88.600	1.310	18.800	0.753	3.250	-0.770
47	194.313	57.910	200.200	492.800	1.490	36.700	0.970	22.950	0.810
48	131.388	25.760	89.100	210.400	1.489	31.000	1.474	10.210	2.420

Table 3. Calculated values of various topological parameters used in the present study

Compd.	W	J	J _{hetZ}	J _{hetm}	J _{hetv}	J _{hete}	J _{hetp}	⁰ χ	¹ χ	² χ	⁰ χ ^v	¹ χ ^v	² χ ^v
1	18	2.540	2.831	2.830	1.834	2.827	1.713	4.284	2.270	1.802	3.179	1.560	1.032
2	18	2.540	3.345	3.344	1.887	3.326	1.694	4.284	2.270	1.802	3.433	1.388	1.069
3	20	2.191	2.290	2.290	1.886	2.289	1.822	4.121	2.414	1.354	3.569	2.023	1.077
4	18	2.540	3.480	3.509	2.540	2.779	2.758	4.284	2.270	1.802	4.552	2.442	1.989
5	18	2.540	2.682	2.682	2.127	2.680	2.044	4.284	2.270	1.802	3.732	1.951	1.257
6	18	2.540	4.267	4.333	2.540	2.920	2.884	4.284	2.270	1.802	4.686	2.519	2.131
7	29	2.993	5.079	5.159	2.993	3.451	3.408	5.155	2.643	2.488	5.690	2.952	2.996
8	516	1.928	2.446	2.446	2.295	2.446	2.267	12.466	7.998	7.735	10.013	5.590	4.719
9	46	3.144	3.761	3.759	2.393	3.754	2.231	5.862	3.181	2.630	4.894	2.260	1.678
10	60	2.279	3.752	3.769	3.135	3.307	3.292	5.983	3.805	3.239	5.577	2.961	2.229
11	31	2.754	3.841	3.875	2.754	3.029	3.004	4.992	2.808	1.922	5.393	3.075	2.140
12	31	2.754	3.518	3.517	2.365	3.510	2.152	4.992	2.808	1.922	4.102	1.984	1.189
13	72	3.074	3.432	3.431	2.305	3.420	2.124	6.406	3.846	2.471	5.723	3.179	1.750
14	62	2.192	3.581	3.596	3.032	3.188	3.175	5.983	3.788	3.365	5.577	2.955	2.309
15	10	1.975	3.083	3.122	1.975	2.234	2.210	3.414	1.914	1.000	3.682	2.104	1.134
16	66	3.389	3.554	3.553	2.895	3.552	2.793	6.784	3.417	4.159	5.679	2.821	2.866
17	32	2.627	3.036	3.034	1.744	3.029	1.606	4.992	2.770	2.183	4.140	1.941	1.304
18	42	2.123	3.021	3.021	3.021	3.021	3.021	5.113	3.394	2.743	4.387	2.411	1.655
19	84	2.346	3.751	3.764	2.909	3.394	2.952	6.853	4.198	3.873	5.947	3.096	2.439
20	133	2.017	2.749	2.748	1.684	2.744	1.562	7.234	4.932	3.646	5.656	3.220	1.885
21	48	2.953	3.427	3.427	2.968	3.425	2.891	5.862	3.126	3.023	4.524	2.115	1.581
22	79	2.716	3.220	3.219	1.927	3.214	1.782	6.406	3.770	2.890	5.438	2.904	1.694
23	151	2.909	3.173	3.173	2.680	3.172	2.599	7.983	4.626	4.072	5.539	3.063	1.995
24	32	2.627	3.446	3.444	1.690	3.435	1.532	4.992	2.770	2.183	4.024	1.904	0.925
25	31	2.754	3.733	3.755	2.965	3.172	3.154	4.992	2.808	1.922	4.837	2.606	1.775
26	174	2.047	2.703	2.702	1.669	2.698	1.549	8.104	5.288	4.475	6.527	3.647	2.473
27	102	3.155	3.776	3.775	2.184	3.768	2.013	7.276	4.181	3.364	5.755	2.957	2.046
28	28	3.168	3.609	3.607	2.183	3.602	2.024	5.207	2.561	2.914	4.908	2.112	2.316
29	168	2.132	2.852	2.851	1.724	2.846	1.596	8.104	5.326	4.253	6.527	3.652	2.424
30	264	1.687	2.427	2.426	1.529	2.423	1.422	8.933	6.449	5.244	7.182	4.230	2.728
31	220	2.691	2.911	2.910	2.093	2.907	1.980	8.364	5.414	3.475	8.065	4.992	3.027
32	48	2.953	3.444	3.442	1.918	3.436	1.760	5.862	3.126	3.023	5.563	2.781	2.234
33	15	2.083	2.321	2.320	1.533	2.317	1.440	3.536	2.500	1.768	3.237	2.077	1.319
34	120	2.595	2.859	2.858	1.923	2.855	1.803	6.950	4.414	2.768	6.651	3.992	2.319
35	15	2.083	2.978	2.977	1.838	2.972	1.712	3.536	2.500	1.768	2.718	1.471	0.793
36	4	1.633	1.868	1.867	1.111	1.864	1.027	2.707	1.414	0.707	2.154	1.023	0.316
37	150	2.446	3.438	3.437	2.258	3.433	2.113	8.268	5.291	4.127	7.049	3.469	2.288
38	28	3.168	5.126	5.191	2.760	3.718	2.927	5.207	2.561	2.914	5.056	2.371	3.289
39	84	2.346	3.936	3.958	3.172	3.381	3.363	6.853	4.198	3.873	6.634	3.439	2.809
40	61	2.231	3.656	3.671	3.078	3.240	3.226	5.983	3.788	3.377	5.577	2.955	2.313
41	125	2.174	3.130	3.129	1.999	3.125	1.863	7.397	4.864	3.703	6.126	3.046	1.880
42	43	2.140	2.799	2.798	1.937	2.795	1.825	5.113	3.432	2.559	3.795	2.052	1.290
43	84	2.346	3.652	3.665	3.172	3.310	3.298	6.853	4.198	3.873	6.500	3.372	2.732
44	9	2.324	2.963	2.962	2.342	2.960	2.249	3.577	1.732	1.732	2.908	1.204	0.908
45	88	2.228	3.018	3.018	2.854	3.017	2.824	6.690	4.305	3.642	5.295	2.865	1.922
46	1	1.000	1.333	1.332	0.512	1.327	0.455	2.000	1.000	0.000	1.447	0.447	0.000
47	307	1.818	1.861	1.861	1.819	1.861	1.812	9.803	6.877	5.655	9.134	6.414	5.072
48	18	2.540	6.215	6.352	3.143	3.740	3.683	4.284	2.270	1.802	4.479	2.077	1.625

Table 4. Correlation matrix showing inter correlation among various parameters and also with $-\log LC_{50}$

	$-\log LC_{50}$	log P	W	J	J_{hetZ}	J_{hetm}	J_{hetv}	J_{hete}	J_{hetp}	${}^0\chi$	${}^1\chi$	${}^2\chi$	${}^0\chi^v$	${}^1\chi^v$	${}^2\chi^v$	
$-\log LC_{50}$	1															
log P	0.892	1														
W	0.432	0.389	1													
J	0.087	-0.067	-0.233	1												
J_{hetZ}	0.395	0.297	-0.291	0.628	1											
J_{hetm}	0.394	0.298	-0.291	0.617	1.000	1										
J_{hetv}	0.563	0.492	-0.080	0.481	0.717	0.713	1									
J_{hete}	0.339	0.185	-0.208	0.818	0.798	0.786	0.657	1								
J_{hetp}	0.569	0.518	-0.111	0.402	0.753	0.753	0.980	0.572	1							
${}^0\chi$	0.560	0.459	0.916	0.037	-0.079	-0.085	0.149	0.112	0.079	1						
${}^1\chi$	0.562	0.485	0.928	-0.139	-0.191	-0.195	0.061	-0.022	0.002	0.975	1					
${}^2\chi$	0.548	0.463	0.882	-0.003	-0.048	-0.053	0.224	0.126	0.157	0.961	0.938	1				
${}^0\chi^v$	0.674	0.622	0.848	0.098	0.078	0.075	0.277	0.150	0.242	0.943	0.913	0.898	1			
${}^1\chi^v$	0.618	0.578	0.855	-0.020	-0.060	-0.061	0.176	-0.030	0.157	0.901	0.909	0.844	0.967	1		
${}^2\chi^v$	0.577	0.543	0.742	0.143	0.173	0.173	0.363	0.129	0.358	0.808	0.761	0.837	0.912	0.894	1	
MW	0.770	0.692	0.728	0.064	0.288	0.288	0.448	0.201	0.459	0.833	0.807	0.826	0.919	0.875	0.892	
MR	0.667	0.636	0.894	-0.062	-0.039	-0.042	0.211	0.045	0.175	0.957	0.962	0.924	0.977	0.960	0.864	
MV	0.585	0.544	0.841	0.095	-0.074	-0.079	0.115	0.079	0.061	0.919	0.903	0.832	0.958	0.953	0.818	
PC	0.605	0.546	0.891	0.042	-0.064	-0.068	0.156	0.061	0.107	0.965	0.953	0.900	0.982	0.975	0.860	
IR	0.674	0.646	0.528	-0.180	0.229	0.229	0.490	0.159	0.492	0.631	0.670	0.716	0.642	0.599	0.628	
ST	0.412	0.268	0.494	-0.044	0.152	0.152	0.353	0.113	0.342	0.588	0.582	0.649	0.512	0.491	0.545	
D	0.524	0.436	0.029	0.093	0.664	0.670	0.617	0.308	0.707	0.131	0.102	0.212	0.251	0.194	0.393	
POL	0.667	0.636	0.894	-0.062	-0.039	-0.042	0.211	0.045	0.175	0.957	0.962	0.924	0.977	0.960	0.864	
	MW	MR	MV	PC	IR	ST	D	POL								
MW	1															
MR	0.896	1														
MV	0.783	0.942	1													
PC	0.856	0.980	0.982	1												
IR	0.808	0.713	0.459	0.587	1											
ST	0.697	0.552	0.326	0.491	0.833	1										
D	0.603	0.215	-0.005	0.119	0.678	0.672	1									
POL	0.896	1.000	0.942	0.980	0.713	0.551	0.215	1								

Table 5. Regression parameters quality of correlation for the entire set of compounds

Model no.	Parameters used	$A_i=(1\cdots\cdots 4)$	B	Se	R^2	R_{Adj}	F-ratio	Q = R/Se
1.	log P	0.8178 (± 0.0612)	1.4712	0.2112	0.7953	0.7908	178.693	4.2225
2.	J_{hetv}	1.2002 (± 0.2601)	0.0538	0.3860	0.3164	0.3016	21.293	1.4572
3.	J_{hete}	0.8275 (± 0.3381)	0.2883	0.4391	0.1152	0.0960	5.990	0.7730
4.	J_{hetp}	1.0200 (± 0.2171)	0.4781	0.3838	0.3243	0.3096	22.079	1.4838
5.	${}^0\chi$	0.3693 (± 0.0806)	0.6124	0.3869	0.3132	0.2983	20.977	1.4465
6.	${}^1\chi$	0.5042 (± 0.1095)	1.0001	0.3863	0.3155	0.3006	21.199	1.4540
7.	${}^2\chi$	0.5219 (± 0.1175)	1.2767	0.3905	0.3003	0.2851	19.745	1.4033
8.	${}^0\chi^v$	0.5249 (± 0.0849)	0.0828	0.3451	0.4537	0.4418	38.195	1.9518
9.	MW	0.0245 (± 0.0030)	-0.1751	0.2978	0.5930	0.5841	67.019	2.5858

Table-5 (contd.)

10.	MR	0.0742 (± 0.0122)	0.4315	0.3479	0.4446	0.4325	36.818	1.9166
11.	MV	0.0223 (± 0.0046)	0.2183	0.3788	0.3418	0.3275	23.888	1.5434
12.	PC	0.0091 (± 0.0018)	0.3250	0.3716	0.3663	0.3526	26.595	1.6287
13.	IR	12.5064 (± 2.0208)	-15.4238	0.3449	0.4543	0.4425	38.303	1.9542
14.	ST	0.0681 (± 0.0222)	0.6655	0.4253	0.1701	0.1521	9.431	0.9697
15.	d	2.9252 (± 0.7016)	-0.2874	0.3977	0.2742	0.2585	17.381	1.3167
16.	J_{hetv}	0.3491 (± 0.1569)	0.7950	0.2027	0.8156	0.8074	99.501	4.4554
	log P	0.7440 (± 0.0674)						
17.	log P	0.7428 (± 0.0669)	1.0561	0.2019	0.8170	0.8088	100.424	4.4769
	$^1\chi$	0.1512 (± 0.0655)						
18.	log P	0.7070 (± 0.0744)	0.8693	0.2011	0.8185	0.8104	101.434	4.4988
	$^0\chi^v$	0.1514 (± 0.0632)						
19.	log P	0.7377 (± 0.0646)	0.8617	0.1982	0.8238	0.8159	105.178	4.5794
	$^0\chi$	0.1254 (± 0.0465)						
20.	log P	0.7718 (± 0.0589)	0.5825	0.1959	0.8278	0.8202	108.174	4.6444
	ST	0.0309 (± 0.0106)						
21.	log P	0.6316 (± 0.0757)	0.6426	0.1888	0.8401	0.8330	118.201	4.8547
	MW	0.0093 (± 0.0026)						
22.	log P	0.6548 (± 0.0742)	-0.0892	0.1826	0.8536	0.8437	85.547	5.0597
	MW	0.0085 (± 0.0026)						
	J	0.3234 (± 0.1601)						
23.	log P	0.5925 (± 0.0742)	0.3743	0.1801	0.8576	0.8479	88.313	5.1420
	MW	0.0188 (± 0.0048)						
	$^2\chi^v$	-0.4097 (± 0.1763)						
24.	log P	0.6187 (± 0.0706)	-0.4304	0.1756	0.8647	0.8554	93.704	5.2955
	MW	0.0086 (± 0.0025)						
	J_{hete}	0.3909 (± 0.1383)						
25.	log P	0.6140 (± 0.0702)	-0.5603	0.1693	0.8770	0.8656	76.682	5.5315
	MW	0.0194 (± 0.0045)						
	J	0.3926 (± 0.1504)						
	$^2\chi^v$	-0.4802 (± 0.1678)						
26.	log P	0.5849 (± 0.0694)	-0.5883	0.1684	0.8784	0.8671	77.636	5.5655
	MW	0.0171 (± 0.0045)						
	J_{hete}	0.3615 (± 0.1333)						
	$^2\chi^v$	-0.3646 (± 0.1656)						

Modeling $-\log LC_{50}$ using 48 compounds :

One-variable model :

The best one-variable model obtained is reported below.

$$-\log LC_{50} = -1.4712 - 0.8178 (\pm 0.0612) \log P \quad (9)$$

$$n = 48, Se = 0.2112, R^2 = 0.7953, F = 178.693, Q = 4.4225$$

Here and here after the n is the total number of compounds; Se is the standard error of estimation; R^2 is the

correlation coefficient; R^2_{Adj} is the adjusted R^2 ; F is the Fisher's ratio and Q is the Pogliani's quality factor²⁷⁻²⁹ which is the ratio of R/Se.

In the above mentioned model the coefficient of log P is positive it means that the octonal-water partition coefficient plays a positive role towards the acute toxicity. For this one-variable model the R^2 value comes out to be 0.7953 showing that the model explains about 79% of variance in data.

The successive regression indicated that addition of

molecular weight (MW) in the above model yields two-variable model with still better quality.

Two-variable model :

$$-\log LC_{50} = 0.6426 + 0.0093 (\pm 0.0026) MW + 0.6316 (\pm 0.0757) \log P \quad (10)$$

$$n = 48, Se = 0.1888, R^2 = 0.8401, R^2_{Adj} = 0.8330, F = 118.201, Q = 4.8547$$

The addition of MW is also justified as the adjusted R^2 (R^2_{Adj}) is increased significantly. The addition of MW to the log P shows a significant improvement in the R^2 value from 0.7953 to 0.8401. The quality of the model (Q) changes from 4.4225 to 4.8547 and the Se value decreases from 0.2112 to 0.1888. Here the coefficient of the MW is small and positive which shows that compounds with higher molecular weight will play positive role in exhibiting towards $-\log LC_{50}$.

Three-variable model :

Addition of Balaban type J_{hete} index to the above model gave a three-variable model having $R^2 = 0.8647$. The improved R^2_{Adj} value indicates that J_{hete} has a fair share in this model.

$$-\log LC_{50} = -0.4304 + 0.0086 (\pm 0.0025) MW + 0.6187 (\pm 0.0706) \log P + 0.3909 (\pm 0.1383) J_{hete} \quad (11)$$

$$n = 48, Se = 0.1756, R^2 = 0.8647, R^2_{Adj} = 0.8554, F = 93.704, Q = 5.2955$$

J_{hete} has positive coefficient meaning thereby that extended connectivity and presence of hetero atoms plays a positive role towards the exhibition of acute toxicity ($-\log LC_{50}$).

Addition of second-order valance connectivity index ${}^2\chi^v$ to the above three-parametric model yielded a four-parametric model which is given below.

Four-variable model :

$$-\log LC_{50} = -0.5883 + 0.0171 (\pm 0.0045) MW + 0.5849 (\pm 0.0694) \log P + 0.3615 (\pm 0.1333) J_{hete} - 0.3646 (\pm 0.1656) {}^2\chi^v \quad (12)$$

$$n = 48, Se = 0.1684, R^2 = 0.8784, R^2_{Adj} = 0.8671, F = 77.636, Q = 5.5655$$

Here, the coefficient of ${}^2\chi^v$ is negative. This indicates that the decrease in second-order valance connectivity

which is related to branching will favor the $-\log LC_{50}$ value.

To confirm our results we calculated $-\log LC_{50}$ values for the compounds using four-variable model and compared them with their observed values. Such comparison is shown in Table 6. A close look at this table shows that the residuals are less in most of the com-

Table 6. Observed and estimated $-\log LC_{50}$ values using model 26 (Table 5)

Compd.	Obs. $-\log LC_{50}$	Est. $-\log LC_{50}$	Residual
1	0.838	0.901	-0.063
2	0.839	0.929	-0.090
3	1.601	1.604	-0.003
4	2.907	2.937	-0.030
5	1.305	1.639	-0.334
6	3.214	3.145	0.069
7	3.917	3.715	0.202
8	4.696	4.604	0.092
9	2.552	2.650	-0.098
10	3.411	4.224	-0.813
11	3.346	3.707	-0.361
12	2.014	2.724	-0.710
13	1.818	2.041	-0.223
14	4.015	4.152	-0.137
15	2.931	2.567	0.364
16	1.089	2.009	-0.920
17	0.637	1.284	-0.647
18	3.549	2.960	0.589
19	4.277	4.172	0.105
20	2.604	2.720	-0.116
21	2.860	1.813	1.047
22	3.810	3.022	0.788
23	3.178	2.462	0.716
24	2.583	2.324	0.259
25	4.184	3.567	0.617
26	2.735	2.974	-0.239
27	2.758	2.461	0.297
28	2.118	2.212	-0.094
29	2.735	3.046	-0.311
30	4.620	4.663	-0.043
31	4.690	4.426	0.264
32	3.040	2.474	0.566
33	1.520	1.269	0.251
34	3.600	3.700	-0.100
35	3.040	2.144	0.896

Table-6 (contd.)

36	-0.510	0.576	-1.086
37	3.870	3.963	-0.093
38	2.690	2.939	-0.249
39	4.790	5.078	-0.288
40	4.270	4.310	-0.040
41	3.070	3.474	-0.404
42	2.280	1.803	0.477
43	4.740	4.738	0.002
44	0.850	1.002	-0.152
45	2.870	2.778	0.092
46	0.060	-0.012	0.072
47	2.270	2.029	0.241
48	3.470	3.831	-0.361

pounds suggesting that this model is best for predicting $-\log LC_{50}$ values. Further confirmation is obtained by plotting a graph between the observed and estimated $-\log LC_{50}$ values which is depicted in Fig. 1. On the basis of Pogliani's quality factor (Q which is the ratio of R/Se) the highest value is obtained for eq. (12) (model 26, Table 5) suggesting that the four-variable model [eq. (12)] is the most appropriate model for modeling $-\log LC_{50}$ of the present set of compounds.

Fig. 1. Correlation between observed and estimated $-\log LC_{50}$ using model-26 [eq. (12)].

Confirmation on the basis of adjusted- R^2 :

In order to ascertain whether or not the models recorded in Table 5 and discussed above are statistically good, we have used variation of R^2_{Adj} in the development of the proposed models. The adjustable- R^2 or R^2_{Adj} takes into account of adjustment of R^2 . Generally it is given by the following expression. It helps in explaining whether or not the added parameters have favorable con-

tribution to the proposed model.

$$R^2_{Adj} = 1 - (1 - R^2) \frac{n - 1}{n - k - 1} \quad (13)$$

Here n is the number of compounds used in the present study. R^2 is the coefficient of variation and k is the number of parameters used in the proposed model. If a variable added that does not contribute its fair share to the model then the R^2_{Adj} will actually decline. This parameter R^2_{Adj} is particularly important when the number of independent variables is larger relative to the sample size. The R^2 will always increase when an independent variable is added to the model. However, if R^2_{Adj} is gradually increasing it means that all the added parameters are contributing their fair share to the proposed models.

Cross validation :

The proposed models were validated by the leave-one-out cross validation procedure and the parameters obtained thereby are reported in Table 7. PRESS (predicted residual sum of squares) appears to be the most important cross validation parameter accounting for a good estimate of the real predictive error of the models. Its value less than SSY (sum of squares of response value) indicates that the model predict better than the chance and can be considered statistically significant. In our case $PRESS \ll SSY$ indicating that all the models obtained are statistically significant. The ratio $PRESS/SSY$ can be used to calculate approximate confidence intervals of prediction of new compounds. To be a reasonable and significant QSAR model the ratio $PRESS/SSY$ should be less than 0.4 ($PRESS/SSY < 0.4$) and the value of this ratio smaller than 0.1 indicates an excellent model. A close observation of Table 7 shows that except the mono parametric model [eq. (9)] all other models have the $PRESS/SSY$ ratio more or less or nearer to 0.1 indicating that all the proposed models are have best predicting capacity. R^2_{CV} is the cross validated squared correlation coefficient. The highest R^2_{CV} value for four-variable model [eq. (12)] confirms our results. The two important cross-validation parameters uncertainty in prediction (S_{PRESS}) and predictive squared error (PSE) also favour our results.

However, just to obtain further confirmation of our results the entire data set of 48 compounds were divided

Table 7. Cross validated parameters for the best mono-, bi-, tri- and tetra-parametric models

Model no.	Parameters used	PRESS/SSY	Q^2_{ext}	S_{PRESS}	PSE	PE	6PE
1.	log P	0.2574	0.7426	0.5886	0.5762	0.0196	0.1181
21.	log P	0.1903	0.8097	0.5259	0.5092	0.0153	0.0923
24.	MW log P	0.1565	0.8435	0.4893	0.4685	0.0130	0.0781
26.	MW J_{hete} log P MW J_{hete} $2\chi^v$	0.1384	0.8616	0.4692	0.4441	0.0116	0.0701

into training set (consisting of 32 compounds) and test (16 compounds) sets. The compounds **3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24, 27, 30, 33, 36, 39, 42, 45, 48** were taken as test set and the remaining compounds as training set. It is worth mentioning that external validation of a model means that the model which has been developed from a training set will be applied to predict the response of the compounds of test set and finally the predicted values of the test set will be compared to the corresponding observed values. We have therefore, used the four-variable model for investigating its predictive ability for training and test sets. The results obtained are given below.

For training set :

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\log LC_{50} = & -0.209 + 0.6386 (\pm 0.0772) \log P \\
 & + 0.2424 (\pm 0.1685) J_{hete} + 0.0166 \\
 & (\pm 0.0048) MW - 0.3968 \\
 & (\pm 0.1703) 2\chi^v \quad (14)
 \end{aligned}$$

$n = 32$, $Se = 0.1567$, $R^2 = 0.9020$, $R^2_{Adj} = 0.8875$, $F = 62.122$, $Q = 2.1626$

$PRESS/SSY = 0.1086$, $R^2_{CV} = 0.8914$, $S_{PRESS} = 0.4440$, $PSE = 0.4078$, $PE = 0.0115$

The predicted values of $-\log LC_{50}$ of training data set using the above model are recorded in Table 1 and plotted against their experimental values. Such a correlation is demonstrated in Fig. 2. The above reported model [eq. 14)] has further been used to predict the $-\log LC_{50}$ values of remaining 16 compounds which are used as test set. Such predicted values are also recorded in Table 1. The predicted R^2 value for the test set has been obtained by

plotting a graph between observed and estimated $-\log LC_{50}$ values for the compounds and is demonstrated in Fig. 3. The R^2_{pred} , or Q^2_{ext} comes out to be 0.8122 confirming that the proposed model is meaningful.

Fig. 2. Correlation between observed and estimated $-\log LC_{50}$ using [eq. (14)].

Fig. 3. Correlation between observed and estimated $-\log LC_{50}$ using test set.

The above findings confirms that for modeling acute toxicity ($-\log LC_{50}$) of present set of compounds a four-variable model containing $\log P$, MW, J_{hete} and ${}^2\chi^v$ is most appropriate model.

Conclusions :

On the basis of the obtained results we have made the following conclusions :

(i) Topological and physico-chemical parameters along with $\log P$ are capable for the prediction of acute toxicity for the present set of compounds,

(ii) $\log P$ plays a dominating role for prediction of acute toxicity $-\log LC_{50}$,

(iii) Increase in Molecular weight (MW) favors $-\log LC_{50}$, and

(iv) Decrease in second order valence connectivity (${}^2\chi^v$) favors $-\log LC_{50}$.

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